

Sociological Bout on the ‘Kushlization’ of Sierra Leonean Juveniles: A Freetown Clogging Communal Health Apocalypse

Mohamed Bangura

Lecturer One, Department of Sociology and Social Work, University of Sierra Leone, Fourah Bay College, Sierra Leone

Abstract

Sierra Leone’s illegal narcotic utilization enigma has augmented considerably amidst the ultimate dual decades [1]. Of specific concern has been the rising drift in narcotic or drug utilization among Sierra Leonean adolescents and juveniles [2]. Frequently utilized narcotics in Sierra Leone include Kush or K2, Marijuana, Tramadol, and to familiar stretch Cocaine. In this sociological inquiry, the researcher discusses worsen narcotic utilization amidst the ultimate dual decades in Sierra Leone, and how it is a grave imminent community health apocalypse. This sociological inquiry intends to scan the rudimentary incentives of the juveniles narcotic abusers and their rapport with their families and to pinpoint dilemmas and necessitates that juvenile narcotic abusers are encountering. The essential insistence is to diagnose the crux mainsprings of narcotic abuse and to entrust the family functional function for neutralization of narcotic abuse in the cultural community. The objective of this sociological inquiry is to diagnose the central root of narcotic abuse, situating attention into ‘Kush’ as the principal narcotic that is being abused amongst adolescents and juveniles addicts. The inquiry methodology entailed a review of books, direct social dialogues, focus cohort social dialogues and internet sites. A random selection was done to choose fourteen addicts who live in the streets of Freetown for questioning. A critical review of narcotic utilization mitigation programs right through the nation is required to secure that they are customized to adolescents and juveniles, a springing critical population for whom these benevolences are indispensable. Invigorating social safety groundwork, narcotic regulative schemes and statute implementation is desperately enforced to resist this imminent communal health apocalypse. The inquiry summarized that to accomplish this, a multi-stakeholder crucial path for cultural community consciousness, jurisdictional transformations to secure punitive measures for suppliers and increased juvenile offenders social contingencies are imperative.

Introduction

Pervious boundaries have witnessed narcotics like Kush and Cocaine locating their path illicitly into the nation in immense quantities. To additionally synthesize aforementioned, domestic formation is directly also rife with Kush and fructose talc, which is essentially illicitly processed and dispersed all over Sierra Leone (2023). In the previous, narcotic utilization was a familiar trait among derelict juveniles ‘Raray bois’(Criminal boys) who affianced in this behavior for multiple grounds, amidst them lightening exhausting circumstances, hoisting bravery for involvement in

crook engagements and as stupefying narcotics to assist them slumber. Nonetheless, extremely lofty jobless levels in Sierra Leone, accompanied with destitution and hopelessness, have generated in augmenting figures of juvenile nationals also transforming to utilizing narcotics as a direction of amusement (2022). This has been magnified by the prepared handiness and reasonability of these narcotics to adolescents and juveniles as they relate within their social bands. The prevailing posture of enormous rise in costs of eatable stuffs might further have compounded the circumstance as juvenile,

More Information

How to cite this article: Bangura M. Sociological Bout on the ‘Kushlization’ of Sierra Leonean Juveniles: A Freetown Clogging Communal Health Apocalypse. *Eur J Med Health Res*, 2024;2(1):75-82.

DOI: 10.59324/ejmhr.2024.2(1).11

Keywords:

narcotic abuse,
‘Kush’,
adolescents,
narcotic regulative schemes,
family impact,
Sociological,
Juveniles,
Communal,
Health, Freetown.

This work is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License. The license permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, on the condition that users give exact credit to the original author(s) and the source, provide a link to the Creative Commons license, and indicate if they made any changes.

involving those of formal education bracket; spot themselves stuck in this occurrence (2023), with constrained entertaining hustles, incredibly in prominent density cultural communities.

The lofty occurrence of narcotic utilization amidst Sierra Leonean Juveniles and its fatal upshots oblige extra Sierra Leonean sociological research into its causation suitable to accommodate further appropriate estimates to curb this social malaise. Albeit no extensive communal sociological inquiry of narcotic utilization exists in Sierra Leone, this social malaise has been recounted broadly [3]. The upshots of narcotic utilization amidst Sierra Leonean juveniles involve delinquent intimacy attitude with its transpiring peril of contracting social disease [4], the mitigated opportunities of acquiring job consequent of academy maverick and augmented brutality and destitution.

Albeit a literature review of narcotic utilization by Sierra Leonean juveniles offers multiple justifications for this phenomenon, they are extremely usually analyzed in a fragmental style and not perceived in their social bond inside a broader sociological construction. The grounds for narcotic utilization amidst juveniles furnished in this sociological inquiry, expressly the susceptibility of juveniles, the downward fulfillment of speculative conducts, destitution and joblessness and extensive communal drives, are previously not appropriately located inside an extensive conceptual structure that could deliver as a cornerstone for instructions to curb this trouble. The literature nonetheless depicts an increasing interest for the demand to perceive the causation of narcotic utilization amidst juveniles generally. This sociological inquiry makes a contribution by depicting that the inquiry of the grounds for the predicament inside a wider social ambience which permits for comprehending them in their social bond provides regarding its solving. But also would it develop in enhanced approaches to curb narcotic utilization among Sierra Leonean juveniles, it would also curb pertained predicaments like brutality and destitution and would consequently impact favorably on Sierra Leonean Juvenile's objective and cognitive health [5].

Literature Review

Narcotic and alcohol abuse in Sierra Leone are alarming and a root source or patron to multiple economic, health and social predicaments distressing the populace. Narcotic reliance statistics depict that narcotic ingestion (Kush and marijuana) in Sierra Leone doubles the Mano River Basin norm and second to none in the Basin. The norm bracket of narcotic reliance in Sierra Leone is twelve and twenty four years and growing [6]. Sierra Leone is among the top three narcotics and alcohol abusers in the Mano River Basin. For every hundred folks, fifteen have a narcotic predicament and for every five Leones in circulation, five Leones are associated to the narcotic abuse

predicament [7]. The principal narcotics being abused are 'Kush', marijuana and cocaine. Collectively, the triad narcotics recorded for over eighty six percent of all cases handled for narcotic abuse in 2023. Between individuals treated for jones, thirty eight percent were handled for 'Kush' reliance, preceded by marijuana at twenty three percent and cocaine at nineteen percent. The prevailing information at Mano River Basin threshold proposes that illegal narcotic utilization among extremely juvenile folks is restricted to a diminutive splinter group who explore with narcotics at an extremely initial social bracket. Frequent utilization among the extremely juvenile is strange quite as is partially contemplated in the Mano River Basin data on folks observing narcotic prescription. Among those who commence utilizing narcotics at an extremely juvenile social bracket, social manifest proposes that prematurely trail with hallucinatory narcotics, involving shag and booze, is linked with an augmented peril of breeding narcotic troubles subsequently in life. Constant narcotic utilization among the under fifteens is terribly often stumbled among a greatly dubious cohort group of the social population, in whom narcotic utilization is merged with other synchronic or antecedent cognitive and social upsets and might holistically be a tag of social predicaments or of a rudimentary acoustic social route that requires community intervention [8].

Narcotic social abuse is a universal challenge with injurious impacts on health, wealth and safety of nations. In Sierra Leone narcotic abuse has been linked with felony, interpersonal brutality, perilous carnal conduct (with nursed augmented peril of AIDS obtainment and STI prevalences), adverse health druggies and psychological effect to their households. Nicotine and booze are holistically the most usually utilized narcotics amongst Sierra Leonean youth. These two narcotics are also the most tried with amongst youth. Because they are both legal, vast consider them tolerable and 'lenient'. This notwithstanding substantial health and social effect linked with them. Despite harmful narcotic abuse is usual in Sierra Leone, 'Kush' is the most usually utilized illegal narcotic amongst juvenile. An inquiry by [1] concluded that of Sierra Leonean Portloko youths had ever utilized at least one illegal narcotic such as marijuana and tobacco. This digit is the highest in the district. Granting the medical and social trauma generated by these narcotics, it is significant to comprehend the stretch of their utilization amongst sub social classes and prospect the efficient paths to curb them.

The Micro Network of Social Peer Pressure

Both qualitative and quantitative sociological research depicts the relevance of social peer pressure as a pivotal element for narcotic utilization amongst Sierra Leonean juveniles. On this detail, it was discovered that

juveniles social approval by their peers are immensely treasured [9]. Surrendering to cohort social pressure to utilize narcotics was also mentioned by [10] who discovered that social peers had immense regard respect for the opinions of their social associates of their peer cohorts. Interviewees aforesaid that they would rather talk over their social troubles with someone of their age bracket or cohort than with tutors, guardians or parents or any household associate. Sociological research conducted by [11] disclosed that peers were regarded the primary suppliers of assistance and that they comprised the most dominant elements generating narcotic utilization amongst juveniles. Social peer pressure as element for narcotic utilization is also inferred by an inquiry embarked by [12] who discovered, with an eighty eight point nine percent accuracy, that juveniles who disclosed deep-rooted dipsomania were essentially probably to have comrades who utilize booze or liquor. Based on [13], adolescents were three to six times further potentially to have utilized liquor and to have been involved in satiate boozing in the following month if they had comrades who utilized liquor. Their social inquiry depicted that adolescents were gifted their foremost booze by comrades rather than other folks.

Inadequate Functional Modeling

The significance of the impression of parents who utilized narcotics on their adolescent children was also demonstrated by [14]. They discovered that parents utilization of narcotics in terms of smoking nicotine and cannabis and consuming liquor, and emphasize parents utilization of liquor and cannabis bore an important interaction to the consistency of their adolescent children's utilization of illicit narcotics.

Relating the impression of parental conduct on their children, [15] disclosed that parental conduct of discipline, lodged in parent's social education of their children's social engagements and restriction is essentially predictive of lesser thresholds of liquor and nicotine utilization. They also mentioned that overt but not covert marital violence was linked with the utilization of the revealed narcotics.

Ecosystem of Cultural Community Tolerance

Cultural community antisocial conduct, in this context, refers to adults' utilization or peddling of illicit narcotics and their having been arrested by the police in terms of illicit narcotics, whilst the theory 'subjective adult norms' refers to adults encouraging the utilization of cannabis, and accepting to their adolescent children's consumption of liquor and smoking of cigarettes. [16] discovered that cultural community antisocial conduct, run down communities and community affirmation could be significantly linked to secondary school students utilization of domestic hard liquor in the provinces or western urban Freetown. Nonetheless,

assertion conveyed as acknowledgement and admission of duty perfect, reported an important interaction to adolescents declining from boozing domestic liquor.

An important interaction between narcotic utilization and cultural community liberality was depicted by [17] who mentioned associations between adolescents who had been stupefied and cultural communities where liquor could be accessed comfortably and where police stop to react to juvenile's utilization of liquor.

Destitution and Joblessness

Based on [18], destitution is an indicator of narcotic utilization hence the latter might present as a mechanism of subsisting with the commonplace coercion of destitution. The functional function that joblessness plays in narcotic utilization should, based on [19], be perceived in terms of its interaction to morale failure and social retrogression generating from the destitution that joblessness ignites. The existing lofty joblessness threshold of 3.60 % among 18 and above, as revealed at the end of 2023 [20] presents an interpretation for the broadly observed destitution in Sierra Leone. Narcotic utilization by adults, geared at escaping frustration, could impress adolescents who chase adulthood to put up similar social conduct which, in turn, could negatively impress their peers, generating an augmented mitigation in opportunities of acquiring job.

Basically, it is destitution and joblessness and the absence of any recreational centers that leave young folks with an emotion of despondency and mediocrity. If they perceive no anticipation of ever acquiring a noble employment and sufficient earning to reside a traditional existence, pursuing oblivion via narcotics or liquor becomes a tempting escape route [21].

Social Brutality

Literature discloses reciprocity between social brutality and narcotic utilization by Juveniles. An expansive social research project headed by [22] at Secondary Schools in Freetown, Western Urban Sierra Leone disclosed that respondents from this metropolis considered narcotic utilization to be an essential element for brutality, which depicted, previously, in physical brutality geared towards cultural communities. The connection between the utilization of narcotics and brutality would interpret that the roots of social brutality disclosed in the mentioned inquiry, involving challenged cultural communities, tribal conflicts, social cliques and tribal tensions, would also connect to narcotic utilization since each of them has the ability to augment the depression observed by the juvenile at divergent cultural domains, thereby amplifying juveniles susceptibility to narcotics. [23] speculate that lofty thresholds of communal stress would relate to augmented narcotic utilization by adolescents. In this respect they reveal contemporary

stressors which happen in cultural communities, expressly existing brutality and felony, lofty levels of joblessness, automation transformations and the HIV contagion.

Macro-Structure

Lofty thresholds of cultural communal anxiety in the social space would induce narcotic utilization by juveniles [24], either rightly or discursively. Whether nuisances integrate right mainsprings for narcotic utilization amongst juveniles or bring about the rights mainsprings in the microstructure to come into social role and sustain on each other, they should not be perceived as being dissimilar to vistas in the macrostructure.

Sierra Leone's contemporary technological social indulgence introduced a current and fair-minded standard network which has been given opportunities for previously deprived Sierra Leonean juveniles. Ultimately, this social digital freedom, because of its immensity, could induce vulnerable adolescents to demand adulthood further passionately and to precede improper "adult" conduct such as boozing and narcotizing. Holistic standards which are recently stressed, expressly those of being in dominion of employment skills, being motivated and stipulating on one's right could also impact narcotic utilization amongst Sierra Leonean juveniles. In themselves these social standards are impressive, but if juveniles become impulsive in their chase of them, they could ignite augmented depression which would establish them further susceptible to narcotic utilization [25].

Further critical pertaining relating to narcotic utilization by juveniles relates the difficulty observed by the government to establish adequate employments to uplift financially disadvantaged cultural communities in the social space of existence. Adequate employment chances would impact impressively on the eradication of destitution and mitigate inappropriate role epitome by parents and friends who utilize narcotics to evade from their hopelessness. It could be revealed that destitution would rightly or discursively have a gloomy impact on the mental health of juveniles discovering themselves at the epic of cultural community, thereby establishing them further susceptible to pursue social solace in the utilization of narcotics.

Problem Statement

Comprehending elements for the proliferation of narcotic utilization amongst young folks in Freetown, Sierra Leone.

Social Goals

This sociological inquiry intends to explore the rudimentary mainsprings of the juvenile narcotic abusers and their connection with their households and to recognize troubles and demands that young narcotic abusers are encountering. The central emphasis is to recognize the crux of narcotic abuse and to empower

the household functional function for prevention of narcotic abuse in the cultural community.

Sierra Leone has a grave narcotic usage enigma, as disclosed in the literature. Narcotic abuse imposes economic, health and social costs on persons, households, cultural community and economy in entirety. At the individual threshold, narcotic abuse has been associated to depression, brutal conduct and divergent shapes of felony, involving numerous accidental and premeditated injuries. Cultural community loses the productivity and energies of folks impacted by narcotic abuse. At the macro threshold, prevention and treatment costs linked with narcotic abuse are phenomenal. In Sierra Leone, evidence on the stretch, socio-cultural impact of narcotic abuse as well as its prevention is fragmented and further often not lodged within a comprehensive conceptual framework that could make it simpler to establish approaches and initiatives for curbing the narcotic abuse challenge. Despite much sociological research has been done on the matter, diminutive attempt has been formulated to place all this social fact in a consistent account that will locate in advance the stretch, and impact of the trouble and notate future arbitrations and the developing of initiatives.

Ordinarily, the social goal of this sociological inquiry is to identify the mainspring of narcotic abuse, lodging attention into Kush as the principal narcotic that is being abused in the Freetown municipality. Kush (also known as K2) is a domestic narcotic that has allegedly come into widespread utilization in Sierra Leone since 2022, predominantly in the slum communities, although it is perceived to be emerging in other locations in Sierra Leone as well. The narcotic is mostly portrayed as a mixture of numerous components, and these may differ, nevertheless the main engaging component of the narcotic is fentanyl, tramadol and formalin, mostly whipped with 'Jamba' (local Krio word for Marijuana).

Methodology

The sociological inquiry methodology encompassed a review of books, direct social dialogue, focus cohort dialogues and websites. A random selection was done to choose fourteen 'Kush' addicts who dwell in the streets of Freetown for dialoguing. The volunteers were between the ages of fifteen to twenty two subsequently, amongst the 'Kush' addicts were eight males and six males, and among the respondents were a twenty year old pregnant lady. The principal question directed to them was the factor why they left their homes to dwell in the streets and the reason why they take drugs. The response was similar; ten of them revealed household troubles, involving unequal treatment with family members whom they inhabit with after their parents are deceased or when parents get separated or divorced. Nonetheless, five disclosed

their desire to do a trial with narcotics like liquor and tobacco then eventually commence experimenting robust narcotics like 'Kush'. These five 'Kush' addicts came from impressive households with both parents to look after them but the interest to utilize narcotics propelled them to dwell in the streets. Dialoguing if they can return home to their relatives and be embraced by their relatives, all the five 'Kush' addicts reacted impressively since they departed willingly without being pursued out. However, they even disclose that their relatives mostly come to cajole them to return home and engage a progressive social existence. Dialoging why they rejected to return home and dwell with family they all disclosed that at home their family will not provide them cash to purchase narcotics that is why street social existence is better as they can enlist with gangs and commence looting folks to get cash and sustain their narcotic appetite. Notwithstanding, the nine respondents also disclose that their family did not heed about their welfare, even purchasing secondary school uniforms or assist them to go to secondary school, after observing that sort of bad treatment at home, they turned to street social existence.

Result and Discussion

Majority of the male 'Kush' addicts disclosed that they are not timid to loot or to murder if the prey opposes with his or her properties. Majority of the respondents disclosed that they become very brave when they are under the 'Kush' inducement rather than when they are reasonable. They routinely commit felony when they are under the inducement of 'Kush' they become gallant and further stubborn. The female respondents revealed that they are not able to loot folks; consequently, they lean on men to loot and purchase the 'Kush' in exchange for sexual intercourse. Anybody who brings the 'Kush' will be rewarded with intercourse on that day, they also revealed that they do not have a constant street lover; a street lover is casual for period when he delivers eatables or 'Kush'. The social connection is rigorously sexual intercourse and no love among them. Dialoguing if they utilize safety measures, vast of the respondents disclosed they do not utilize condoms and does not even comprehend where to purchase them. Nonetheless, the whole respondents was conscious that the vast generate of sexually transmitted diseases is unsafe sexual intercourse. They reveal they are not cowed of sexually transmitted diseases because everybody is ultimately going to pass on but individuals pass on in divergent directions. Dialoguing if they understand their HIV status, twelve of the 'Kush' addicts said it is not imperative to comprehend and they will no way go for testing, the prevailing two involving the pregnant lady disclosed testing HIV assured when they got tested after crumbling unwell. The two mentioned they are not

taking any medicine after they concocted the tablets with 'Kush' and gas them. Dialoguing if they will go and receive the tablets afresh to drink, the 'Kush' addicts disclosed they will go and receive the tablets but gas them subsequently.

Nonetheless, eight of the respondents indicate eatable as comfort, they sometimes go for pair or further days lacking eatable, and despite they afford to purchase eatable, ultimately the principal interest is 'Kush' narcotic than eatable. They also disclose that when they are under the inducement the narcotic will make them extremely hungry, so they prefer shoplifting to get something to eat rather than utilizing their paper money on eatable. It was also disclosed that all the cash which they receive is only utilized to purchase 'Kush' narcotic; they propone to wear shabby patches than purchase something to wear. The 'Kush' addicts also disclose they are not apprehensive of being apprehended as they always got captured and acquitted, they also revealed that Pademba Road Correctional Center is also another domicile as they have colleagues there and it is better to be there. Nine 'Kush' addicts regret utilizing 'Kush' and detail street social existence as appalling and bleak. Nonetheless, the five respondents disclosed that street social existence is better than home, they are excited in the streets as they can make cash thus simply by looting folks their laptops, MiPad, mobile phones and cash. Dialoging them where they usually loot folks, they revealed the beach areas, markets, narrow streets and lorry parks They usually loot folks at knife point, their aim is to collect cash and other valuable but not to harm or murder, they can only jab if the sufferer aspires to withstand or coerce them. Dialoging how they take the terrible drug, all the participants revealed that they smoke the 'Kush'.

Dialoging them if there are health professionals who drop by for health education, totally the respondents were steadfast that they never come across anybody from the health agency endeavoring or willing to converse with them about health connected affairs. Dialoging how the endure the frosty weather in streets, three of the fourteen respondents disclosed that when they are under the inducement, they do not feel any coldness as they slumber until the next day without waking up at fixed moments in the course of the night. The rest mentioned they do have coverings which they conceal in fixed locations and only utilize them at night, they disclosed that 'Kush' addicts slumber in divergent domains, ultimately folks have a propensity of stripping others coverings and go to their location were an individual will not discover them, even if an individual discover the location cannot retrieve it because they will clique assault the individual. Completely the four females disclosed that they do not have commands over coverings as the male will retrieve them utilizing

compel or muscle. Nonetheless, the only path to survive the frosty is to share a covering with a man in exchange for sexual intercourse.

The male respondents disclosed they occasionally clash for females as they are fewer than them, occasionally the clash will end via a social contract that addicts give each other rounds that night to have sexual intercourse with a similar woman. Four males can have unsafe sexual intercourse with one female per night without any clash as long they consent on giving each other rounds. Another respondent disclosed that the 'Kush' will make him to evolve a savage sexual appetite and usually clash during the day as women will also be inspecting for cash in the streets. He disclosed that the only path to satiate his appetite is via masturbation. The respondent also divulged he occasionally force himself on a woman (Rape) as occasionally the women will request for cash or 'Kush' foremost prior permitting him to engage in any action. The other male respondent also consented, revealing they always rape especially at night, especially when a woman complains of weariness or request for assistance cash. Another male respondent also divulged that these women are their duties, 'Kush' addicts always protect them in all their demands, even if they rape them, they do not take the matter to the police.

Concept reveals that narcotic abuse has numerous upshots. Despite in Sierra Leone individuals comprehend much about the adverse impacts of liquor and tobacco on person; cultural community and society at large, there is still cocaine, nicotine, heroin, and numerous other narcotics. At a conceptual threshold, narcotics impact the person, cultural community, and municipality as a whole. All its adverse effects cripple all agencies of the economy, involving the health agency. This agency reviews literature on the upshots of narcotic abuse to the person, family or cultural community and municipality at large. On the onslaught it must be considered that this dichotomy is only made to structure the researcher's sociological discourse, the queues separating person, cultural community aftermaths of narcotic abuse are completely blurred.

At the emergence, it is crucial to pinpoint that literature is obvious that the upshots of narcotic abuse vary between women and men, who insinuates any treatment or intervention program must zoom in gender parities. For instance, in a presentation (that is based on a survey conducted between April 2022 and June 2023) made to the Sierra Leone Government by the National Drug Law Enforcement Agency the following upshots of narcotic utilization and abuse on women and girls were noted:

- (a) Seclusion and repudiation were pivotal mainsprings of women narcotic abuse.
- (b) Women were further probably to abuse over the counter pills.

(c) Women narcotic consumers were forty six percent further prone to be sufferers of physical abuse involving rape and incest.

(d) Dependence among women happened further swiftly than men.

Social conduct and engaged in sexual practices further persistently than those who had not utilized this narcotic. In this sociological inquiry, the relationship between narcotic utilization and sexual engagement, brutality for both males and females in metropolitan domains common among 'Kush' addicts. As narcotics tend to motivate instinctive social conduct and damage one's decision, some inquiries have illustrated that those on narcotics are further prone to engage in perilous sexual conduct such as having sexual intercourse without condoms or having numerous partners leading them to contract HIV and Sexually Transmitted Diseases. The psychopharmacological impacts of some narcotics raised the sexual engagement of narcotic consumers, subsequently grooming them to perilous sexual conduct. For instance, the association between narcotic utilization and augmented sexual appetite and recklessness, granting increase to perilous sexual conduct and augmented vulnerability to contracting HIV and other sexually transmitted infections. Nonetheless, 'Kush' addicts divulged having narcotics prior engaging in sexual intercourse. Multiple ladies have become pregnant as the psychopharmacological impacts of narcotics compromise their social existence.

Further social impacts of narcotic abuse to a juvenile involve poor educational accomplishments, welfare reliance joblessness, felony, reliance, destitution, marginalization, social exclusion and brutal conduct. Additionally these backing all and sundry, they successively preserve narcotic ('Kush') abuse.

Upshots

There is agreement among all inquiries appraised that within a cultural household or family milieu, narcotic abuse has grave defeatists impacts, with brutality being the most important enigma. Narcotic utilization is broadly enmeshed in interactive brutality (involving gender-lodged brutality and sexual spank), school brutality, and mostly direct to an unfavorable teaching or knowledge community. At home brutality is dispensed predominantly against women associates, siblings or parents, wives, while at school peers and tutors are the overriding victims. Narcotic utilization substantially marshals to household dysfunctional bonds and social disintegration, economic deprivations and torment, augmented drifts attached with medical and other treatment services for narcotic consumers not able to assist them. Narcotic abuse is also linked with indigent academic output and ambitions and

protracted stay at school. Notwithstanding, narcotic utilization is linked with academic challenges, truancy and quitting out of school. For instance, Marijuana utilization, which is a narcotic of option among Sierra Leonean juveniles has been depicted that it holistically encroaches with education, squat stretch recollection and cognitive dexterity. Furthermore, 'Kush' had unpleasant impacts on physical, memory, and economic well-being, and restricted free privileges via school maverick and apprehension of narcotic consumers in the Western Urban Freetown. Similarly, 'Kush' utilization prompt household conflict, with gloomy upshots on children, involving abandonment and deficient birth aftermaths. At a cultural community threshold, respondents associated 'Kush' utilization to augmented levels of felony, brutality and graft, which sap cultural community solidarity.

Uphshots to cultural community narcotic abuse definitely signify the sparks, ingenuity and aptitudes of the juveniles are not exploited. Narcotic abuse is associated to joblessness, felony, stagnation and even untimely demises. To the cultural community this implies prior productivity and economic growth. In essence, narcotic abuse has a mediated or unmediated social posture on the economy. Other vast costs such as narcotic connected brutality, slashes, murders, ailment, law application and adrift productivity prevail immensely unspecified.

With augmented levels of felony, brutality and graft, this undermined cultural community solidarity. Despite these social statistics do not straightly enunciate to the juvenile; they direct to a grave national or cultural community weight.

Conclusion

Freetown cultural community is on the verge of social crumble due to the menace of narcotics (Kush as principal narcotic) that has obstructed its accomplishment and growth. The domestic precinct is losing millions via vandalization and robbery, predominantly power lines and structures made of aluminum, steel, iron, zinc and copper. Multiple folks are now worried to do their business in Freetown due to the lofty level of felony, the police failed to control the felony level despite they endeavor to bring all the offenders to book but sufficient must be concluded to get rid of felony absolutely.

Recommendations

There is necessity for social effort which conveys the significance of household or family duty to the nurturing of children; the household or family is the most significant structure to train a child about the harms and perils of narcotics. The mosque and church also has a vital role to play by training the children good morals from 'Elaykayhu' (community Islamic center) or Sunday school right via the juvenile phase. The juvenile

phase is the most crucial as young adults endeavor to test further at this phase.

The household or family must observe all their children activities and routine, uplifting them to uphold the five daily Salah or prayers and go to church on Sundays. Most social researchers and scholars miss out the significance of prayer and Allah when they are committing to paper pedagogical details; they inclined focus further on cognitive rationality as the conclusive social solution for troubles. Allah is the ultimate solution for everything, these children must be motivated to cherish Allah God and comprehend His intent for mankind so that they will also acquire better social existence. The household or family social function is vital for a child conduct; numerous narcotic addicts come from fragmented households or families, even if the household family is wealthy but if harmony and affection does not prevail then the child is probably to go off-track. Sociological researchers usually undercut the effect of spiritual intercession as a lasting therapy to the scourge of narcotic abuse. There is grave demand for cultural communities to construct further mosques or Islamic colleges or churches and bible colleges were young juveniles are inspire to attend free of cost and get further religious information about good conduct and devotional education rather than speculative education. Speculative education is al so significant but they can acquire that in schools and colleges. This approach will have an impressive impact in mitigating the menace of narcotic abuse in our cultural communities. The household or family must play the most significant social function then proceeded by the mosque or church, the mosque or church and the household or family must work collectively in exchanging notions on how to construct the social existence of their children.

References

- [1] Bangura SK, Sesay I. The Effect of Drug Abuse on Youths in Portloko Town, Northern Sierra Leone. *Glob J Med Res*, 2022;22(B1):1-7.
- [2] News A. Sierra Leone Trapped by Highly Addictive Drug 'Kush' Youth is 'Dying'. *Redaction Africa News and AFP*. Available at: <https://www.africanews.com/2023/07/21/sierra-leone-trapped-by-highly-addictive-drug-kush-youth-is-dying/>; 2023.
- [3] Fallon K. 'It's like smoking poison': Sierra Leone's youth battle addiction to a mystery drug. *The Gaurdian Organization*. Available at: <https://www.theguardian.com/global-development; 2023>.

- [4] Begum J. What is Drug Addiction. WebMD. Available at: <https://www.webmd.com/mental-health/addiction/drug-abuse-addiction>; 2023.
- [5] Duchschere JE, Reznik SJ, Shanholtz CE, O'Hara KL, Gerson N, Beck CJ, Lawrence E. Addressing a Mental Health Intervention Gap in Juvenile Detention: A Pilot Study. *Evid Based Pract Child Adolesc Ment Health*. 2023;8(2):236-251. doi: 10.1080/23794925.2022.2042873
- [6] Kamara H. Two decades of hostile drug policies: Where is Sierra Leone in all of this? *Manoreporters.com*. Available at: <https://manoreporters.com/news/health/two-decades-of-hostile-drug-policies-where-is-sierra-leone-in-all-of-this/>; 2023.
- [7] Balenger A, Jalloh BJ, Dumbili EW, Swahn MH. Community voices on alcohol harm in Sierra Leone: Perceptions of prevention needs. *PEC Innov*. 2023 Oct 4;3:100227. doi: 10.1016/j.pecinn.2023.100227
- [8] Fullah AM. Homelessness in Sierra Leone: An Overview of Social Work Intervention in Helping Homeless Population. *Eur J Theor Appl Sci*, 2023;1(5):928-934. doi: 10.59324/ejtas.2023.1(5).79.
- [9] Xu S, Yu J, Hu Y. Formation mechanism and prediction model of juvenile delinquency. *Front Psychol*. 2023 May 2;14:1087368. doi: 10.3389/fpsyg.2023.1087368
- [10] Aazami A, Valek R, Ponce AN, Zare H. Risk and Protective Factors and Interventions for Reducing Juvenile Delinquency: A Systematic Review. *Soc Sci*, 2003;12(9):474. doi: 10.3390/socsci12090474.
- [11] Abrams, Z. The psychological science of adolescent behavior and decision-making is reshaping the juvenile justice system. *Monit Psychol*, 2022;53(8).
- [12] Yeng KY, Mohamad ZS. A Case Study on Peer Influence and Peer Pressure in Juvenile Delinquency. *Int J Academ Res Busin Soc Sci*, 2023;13(8). doi:10.6007/IJARBS/v13-i8/17440
- [13] Pramaunururut P, Anuntakulnathee P, Wangroongsarb P, et al. Alcohol consumption and its associated factors among adolescents in a rural community in central Thailand: a mixed-methods study. *Sci Rep*. 2022 Nov 15;12(1):19605. doi: 10.1038/s41598-022-24243-0
- [14] Berg V, Kuja-Halkola R, Khemiri L, Larsson H, Lichtenstein P, Latvala A. Parental alcohol and drug abuse and offspring mortality by age 10: a population-based register study. *Eur J Public Health*. 2022 Nov 29;32(6):933-938. doi: 10.1093/eurpub/ckac142
- [15] Vashishtha R, Pennay A, Dietze PM, Livingston M. The Role of Parental Control and Support in Declining Adolescent Drinking: A Multi-Level Study Across 30 European Countries. *Alcohol Alcohol*. 2022 Jul 9;57(4):470-476. doi: 10.1093/alcalc/agab083
- [16] Boachie MK, Immurana M, Agyemang JK, Ross H. Cigarette Prices and Smoking Experimentation in Sierra Leone: An Exploratory Study. *Tob Use Insights*. 2022 Feb 24;15:1179173X221078189. doi: 10.1177/1179173X221078189
- [17] Mayo CS. Teen drug abuse: Help your teen avoid drugs. *MayoClinic*. Available at: <https://www.mayoclinic.org/healthy-lifestyle/tween-and-teen-health/in-depth/teen-drug-abuse/art-20045921>; 2023.
- [18] Gazso A. Managing More than Poverty When Living With Addiction: Parents' Emotion and Identity Work. *J Famil Iss*, 2023;44(1):46-67. doi: 10.1177/0192513X211041981
- [19] Nolte-Troha C, Roser P, Henkel D, Scherbaum N, Koller G, Franke AG. Unemployment and Substance Use: An Updated Review of Studies from North America and Europe. *Healthcare (Basel)*. 2023 Apr 20;11(8):1182. doi: 10.3390/healthcare11081182
- [20] Trading Economy. Sierra Leone Unemployment Rate. *Trading Economics*. Available at: <https://tradingeconomics.com/sierra-leone/unemployment-rate>; 2023.
- [21] Zisopoulou T, Varvogli L. Stress Management Methods in Children and Adolescents: Past, Present, and Future. *Horm Res Paediatr*. 2023;96(1):97-107. doi: 10.1159/000526946
- [22] Osborne A, James PB, Olorunsaiye CZ, Bangura C, Lebbie A. Cannabis Use and Its Psychosocial Correlates Among School-Going Adolescents in Sierra Leone. *Research Square*, 2023:1-17. doi:10.21203/rs.3.rs-3205061/v1
- [23] Taggart T, Ransome Y, Andreou A, Song I, Kershaw T, Milburn N. Activity Space Assessments to Investigate Neighborhood Exposure to Racism-Related Stress and Related Substance Use Among Young Black Men: Connecticut, 2019. *Am J Public Health*. 2023 Jun;113(S2):S136-S139. doi: 10.2105/AJPH.2023.307254
- [24] O'Mahony S. 'The area I'm from is very rough': Drug users' views on the role of social and economic factors in their experiences of drug-related harm. *J Ethn Subst Abuse*. 2023 Mar 6:1-29. doi: 10.1080/15332640.2023.2177919
- [25] Li J, Wang R, He J, Wang L, Li L. Comparison of the effect of hostility on the level of depression of drug addicts and non-addicts and the mediating role of sense of life meaning between them. *BMC Psychiatry*. 2023 May 21;23(1):350. doi: 10.1186/s12888-023-04856-z

